

Protection to Shoreline Erosion by Construction of Geo-Textile Tube Embankment

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Abstract— Shoreline changes induced by erosion and accretion are natural processes that take place over a range of time duration. They may occur in response to smaller-scale events, such as storms, regular wave action, tides and winds, or in response to large-scale (long-term) events such as glaciation or orogenic cycles that may significantly alter sea levels (rise/fall) and tectonic activities that cause coastal land subsidence or emergence. Hence, most coastlines are naturally dynamic, and cycles of erosion are often an important feature of their ecological character. Wind, waves and currents are natural forces that easily move the unconsolidated sand and soils in the coastal area, resulting in rapid changes in the position of the shoreline.

Experimentation of an innovative technology of construction of Geo-textile tube embankment in a difficult location to fight sea erosion and restoring severely eroded shorelines reducing wave energy and achieving a sustainable coastal embankment with accretion of sand forming a beach pushing out the shorelines towards the sea in post- construction stage duly accepted by the locality .The 2nd coastal protection in India and executions with design & consultancy of IIT, Madras and efficient functioning of the structure encountering seven cyclones instilling a sense of confidence in the area as smelt from the developments. The experience gained in addressing the hindrances encountered, new technology adopted and process of construction can be effectively utilized in other projects can be constructed at a lesser cost. Survey & investigations including bathymetric survey of ocean floor in littoral drift zone area along with model studies of the coastal embankment were taken up by IIT Madras before construction of this pilot project. In post-construction period, the parameters showing improvement of sand accretion in the area need to be surveyed and recorded for a comparative study every year which can indicate the effective performance of the project. The data will be useful for the designers to undertake the design of such protection measures in other locations and ensure the efficient performance of the structure making it cyclone resilient.

Keywords— Geotextile, Shore line Protection, Sustainable ENvironment

I. INTRODUCTION

Orissa has a coast line of around 480 Km and famous for unique array of biological and ecological diversities. Over the years, the behavior of the sea is changing rapidly which threatens the lives and livelihood of coastal people . Orissa coast in general and the Paradeep – Dhamara stretch in Particular has been ravaged by Super Cyclones passing through the reach 2(two) times in the last fifty years during 1971 &1999 , with high surge effects in very severe cyclones in Odisha in 2013 ,2014. & 2018.

Pentha is a seashore village of Rajnagar block in Kendrapara district located south of Dhamara in Paradeep~Dhamara stretch. The shoreline near the village has advanced about 600 meter into the landmass between 1999 to 2012. It has eroded the Rajnagar- Gopalpur Saline embankment very severely for a stretch of 1 km.

The coastal stretch adjacent to Pentha village has been continuously eroded for the last few years. Since July 2007, the erosion continued to be extremely severe and the saline embankment was at stake. Since 2007, Department of Water Resources tried to arrest severe bank erosion by putting big size resin bags filled with sand. But the attempts were not successful. During 2010-11, the saline embankment to protect the village got severely eroded. Sensing the possibility of collapse of the Saline Embankment, a 900 metre long retarded earthen embankment was built on its back side so as to protect the village in case of emergency.

During 2011-12, The Government of India received a credit from the World Bank for the Integrated Coastal Zone Management Project (ICZMP) and Government of Odisha intended to utilize a portion of the funds for the construction of suitable Geo-tube Embankment on the seaside of retarded embankment at Pentha. The Geo-tube embankment is located between the two points 20032'21.57"N-86047.15.12"E and 20032'39.08"N-86047'30.58"E for 505 m length.

Fig 1 : Study Area - Coastline & Saline Embankment positions during 1975 (extracts from Survey of India Map 1975)

Fig 2: Maximum Surge Values as predicated for Odisha Coastline by model studies (2002)

II. CAUSES

The shoreline near village Pentha in Rajnagar block of Kendrapara District has been severely eroded and advanced into the land mass for about 600m. The erosion has been very severe between 1999 to 2014. Traditional method of regular shoreline protection works using wooden stump piling and Big Resin PVC sand bag dumping, construction of retard embankment on the backside of the damaged old embankment did not help. During 2012, the embankment was completely washed away for a length of 350 metre length and endangered village Pentha.

In order to protect the village Pentha & adjoining villages and immediate cultivable land of 6883 Ha from inundation by high waves from sea, protection & strengthening of the embankment was highly essential.

Govt. of Odisha has taken up a Pilot Project under World Bank assistance through Integrated Coastal management Project (ICZMP) to construct a geo-tube embankment at Pentha as a protection measure to the village and adjacent area. Here the main problems are:

- Re-design & planning in locating the structure within the space available between old & retard embankment keeping in view the space becoming narrower after damages inflicted due to 'PHILIN'
- Executions were during low tides only, in 2 spells limited to 3 hours in each spell. In other times, submergence of the area due to high tides.

III.OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

It is a pilot project proposed to develop structural system to face wave action creating threat to the existing embankment.

- As the traditional counter wave embankment strategy was not found feasible, the special pilot design is intended for long term protection.
- It was intended to protect the immediate cultivable land, habitation of a village of Pentha and life and property of the habitants of nearby villages also.
- It was expected to extend protection to the life & property of 6 Gram Panchayats consisting of 58 villages covering an area of 6883 Ha & Population of 41222.

Direct benefits anticipated are:

- Coastal erosion in a critical vulnerable location at Pentha would be prevented.
- 6883 ha of crop land would be protected from salt water intrusion in paddy fields.
- Sea beach would be improved & Sand dune stabilization will be made.

IV.LITERATURE REVIEW

Guidelines for "Protection and control of Coastal Erosion in India" prepared by CSIR National Institute of Oceanography-published by Central Water Commission, Coastal Erosion Directorate, New Delhi

National Assessment of Shoreline change for Odisha Coast published by MoE&F, Govt of India, New Delhi.

Handbook for Flood protection, Anti-Erosion & River Training works.

In consultation with Er. Jugal Kishore Tripathy, Ex-Chief Engineer & Basin Manager, Lower Mahanadi Basin, Bhubaneswar who has executed the Geo-textile embankment at Pentha during his tenure as Executive Engineer, Irrigation Division, Aul in Kendrapara District Presently working as Co-Team Leader, Project management Consultancy, Rengali Irrigation Project-Phase II(JICA).(M. No.9437291732)

V. METHODOLOGY:

Design of geo-tube embankment:

For Installation of Geo-Tube embankment at Pentha in Kendrapara, "Consultancy for survey, design, estimation and construction supervision for installation of geo-tube embankment at Pentha" was awarded to the Department of Ocean Engineering, IIT (Madras), Chennai. The Consultant has conducted the site investigation works, survey, scientific and modeling studies and submitted a final design of the embankment. Clearance of CRZ was obtained from Odisha Coastal Zone Management Authority. Govt. of Odisha was pleased to issue permission to go ahead with the work for construction of Geo-tube embankment at Pentha. The execution of the geo-tube embankment taken up as a pilot Project in the State. The geo-tube embankment was initially designed for a length of 675 metres with a base width of 30m (Fig. 1) for a design water depth of 5m. It was designed with a scour apron for depth of 3m below MSL and a

toe mound of 3m above MSL. The toe mound and scour apron would act as a protection to the structure from scouring action of waves. Four layers of sand filled geo-tubes to be aligned parallel to the shore and gabions boxes are stacked over it. The sand filled geo-tubes would act as protective barrier against tidal waves and gabion boxes would absorb the energy.

Fig-3 – ‘Stand alone’ Geo-tube Embankment as initially designed by IIT(Madras) during 2012-13.

Alignment of geo-tube embankment:

Initially the alignment of Geo-tube embankment was straight and was 5m away from the retarded bund. During Phailin (October 2013), the coastline in the area was severely eroded and the width of the available space was reduced to a narrow strip. Because of the advancement of shore line the embankment base width was reduced from 30m to 24m and Geo-tubes embankment was integrated with the existing retard embankment.(Fig-II)

Fig-4 – Revised Design of Integrated Geo-tube Embankment as modified by IIT(Madras) after Phailin.

Construction of the Geo-tube Embankment.:

Through a National Competitive Bidding (NCB) tender process, the work was awarded to M/s Garware Wall Ropes Ltd, Pune, for an amount of Rs 3295.92 Lakhs. The date commencement & completion for the work initially was 24.07.2013 & 23.06.2014 respectively. Accordingly, the Agency mobilized men and machineries to work site but due to monsoon the work could not be physically started by September 2013.

On 12th October 2013, a very severe cyclonic storm ‘Phailin’ struck Odisha coast near Gopalpur. The cyclonic track generating a wind speed of 50 to 200 Km per hour followed by torrential rain ranging from 100 to 305 mm severely affected the coastal districts. Due to the effect of Phailin, the shoreline at Pentha was seriously eroded. The width of the beach as available earlier to locate the geo-tube embankment as per original approved design was not available in post-Phailin scenario.

This unprecedented incident forced the Department and the Project Consultant to revise the design of the geo-tube limiting to the space available. Accordingly, the Project Consultant submitted a revised design of the embankment and the revised alignment. The Review Committee of Department of Water Resources approved the revised design on 21st May 2014. In the revised design, the geo-tube embankment was made integrated and monolithic with the retard embankment. The length of the geo-tube embankment was revised to be 505 meter instead of 675 metre. The length was reduced in the location of wider beach available in northern side of the village Pentha.

The construction of Geo-tube embankment was taken up as per the design. The working hours were too limited spanning for few hours a day only during low tide periods. During the process of installation of Geo tube, on 13th June 2015, a tube had ruptured longitudinally near a filling port. A Technical Committee inspected the site on 19th June 2015 along with Prof. S.A. Sannasiraj, IIT (Madras) and recommended the modified procedure of tube filling. There after the works of installation of geo-tubes were taken up successfully and all installations are completed during June 2016.

- In order to protect the coastline at Pentha from vulnerable erosion, Integrated Coastal Zone Management Project(ICZMP) & Department of Water Resources, Government of Odisha has taken up an up-to-date method of soft engineering technology which includes construction of a geo-textile tube embankment under the assistance from the World Bank.
- It is a pilot project in the State of Odisha in which a structural system is to be developed to face wave action creating threat to the existing Rajnagar- Gopalpur saline embankment for long term protection.
- Through a NCB Tender, the IIT, Madras was appointed as Project Consultant. They surveyed the site and prepared the designs of the geo-textile tube embankment.
- The work for construction of the geo-tube embankment was awarded to M/s Garware Wall Ropes Ltd, Pune for Rs 3295.93 Lakhs through a NCB Tender process.
- The Contract was signed on 24.07.2013 for a construction period of 11 months. The stipulated date of completion being 23.06.2014. The Drawing was issued.
- The Contractor mobilized men & machineries to site to start the work immediately after monsoon i.e. during October 2013.
- A very-severe cyclone Phailin occurred on 12th October 2013. The shore line at Pentha was severely eroded. The alignment for embankment and design was to be changed to fit in to revised site conditions.

Fig 3: Geo-Textile Tube Embankment as per original approved drawing – designed as an independent embankment & located in between old Embankment and Retard Embankment

Fig 4: Map showing 6883 Ha area being protected by Rajnagar –Gopalpur Saline Embankment

Fig 5: Installation of Geo-tube – Filling in progress

Fig 7: Severely scoured 350 metre length of old embankment is protected by sand bags

Fig 8: Topographical Alignment Of Revised Embankment With Low Tide Level

Fig 9: Geotube laying completed & surfaces to be covered by Shruods and then by Stone filled Rope Gabions.

VI. ADOPTABILITY OF THE STRUCTURE

Geo- textile tube embankment has been selected at Pentha village in Kendrapara district studying the soil characteristics, hydrology, topography, behavior of sea due to regular impact of cyclone in the area, keeping in view the impact on coastal zone by the premier institution IIT, Madras being the Consultant and mostly sharing knowledge with National Institute of Ocean Technology. Also, the efficiency of such type of coastal erosion protection project constructed to protect NH-5 aligned very close to the shoreline at Kakinada in Andhra Pradesh.

Due to threadbare studies by the premier institutions and involvement of Integrated Coastal Management Authority, the technical as well as final wing of World Bank has been satisfied to go ahead for such type of geo- tube project on pilot basis. The site was very difficult in nature for experimentation of a new technology facing serious erosion issues accompanied with impact of strong waves. The site was also quite challenging as during construction with model studies and morphology of the area, there has been large scale damage to the original embankment due to impact of cyclone 'PHYLIN' in Oct' 2013. There was no space for retarding the embankment as the shoreline was very close to the back yard of houses of village. Most of all, the locality was not ready for experimentation of the new technology in their area. When the locality felt the efficacy of the structure during the impact of cyclone 'HUDHUD' in Oct' 2014, they supported whole heartedly for the constructions.

VII. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

- The length of the Geo tube embankment has been revised and reduced from 675 mtr to 505 mtr in consideration of the extra width of beach and old embankment available in the Northern direction.
- The Revised cost of the Project is Rs 3324.00 Lakhs as against the Agreement value of Rs 3295.93 Lakhs.
- The contractor had been granted extension of the 'intended completion date' up to 30.6.2016. The revised work program was submitted by the Contractor to complete the work by 30.6.2016. But the work was completed by 15.6.2016.
- The performance of the structure is quite encouraging despite the structure has been subjected to strong waves due to repeated cyclones in the meantime.

Table 1: The Geo-textile Tube materials were tested in 4 numbers of National level Laboratories in India & the Test results obtained were satisfying the standard specifications.

Sl. No	Property	Tender Specification	IIT-Madras	BTRA – Mumbai		CSMRS - Delhi	Remarks
1	Mass per unit area, g/m ²	350	379.4	354	354.5	354	Okay
2	Tensile Strength (Warp), kN/m	80	87	91.1	90.0	83	Okay
3	Tensile Strength (Weft), kN/m	80	82.7	87.7	81.3	81	Okay
4	Trapezoid tearing strength (Warp), N	1600	1871	1700	1823	1680	Okay
5	Trapezoid tearing strength (Weft), N	1600	1780.6	1821	1920	1650	Okay
6	Elongation(Warp),%	8-15%	N.C	19.7	21.9	25	Okay
7	Elongation(Weft),%	8-15%	N.C	22.5	22.7	25	Okay
8	Puncture strength, N	600	1310	1329	1392	1020	Okay
9	Apparent Opening Size, μ m	250	225	< 250	< 250	250	Okay
10	Water Flow, L/m ² /s	-	Indian Institute of Technology Madras	22.5	20	9/11/2015	Okay

VIII. CONCLUSION

- The installation of the geo-textile tube embankment is successfully completed during June 2022 as a pilot project in Odisha.
- The performance of the embankment is under observation since completion of the structure and to be critically observed during future years also, so that the same can be adopted in other weak and vulnerable Zones with the experience and effectiveness of this project.
- As on date, from the observations it reveals that there has been gradual accretion of sand in sea side over the years and as learnt shoreline erosion to some extent takes place during the impact of cyclones in the area.
- As this being the 2nd pilot project in India, the information on the mode of executions and further observations will certainly give a clear picture on the rate of accretion and longevity of the structure.

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